

DIMORPHISM IN SULPHANILYLBENZAMIDE DERIVATIVES

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Alkyl derivatives of sulphanilylbenzamide exist in dimorphic forms. Method of isolation and general properties have been recorded.

N¹-Benzoylsulphanilamide (sulphanilylbenzamide) has recently been shown (Swyer and Young, *Brit. Med. J.*, 1945, *i*, 149; Bose and Ghosh, *Indian Med. Gaz.*, 1945, *80*, 293) to be efficacious against bacillary dysentery. The entrance of this drug into the field of chemotherapy led us to make a survey of its physical and chemical properties. In the course of this study the compound was converted into its silver salt and was subsequently treated with alkyl halides. The latter reaction afforded alkylated sulphanilylbenzamide but it was found that this compound occurred in two distinct crystalline forms. The conditions for the isolation of these dimorphs and their general properties are herein recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reaction with Ethyl Iodide.

Sulphanilylbenzamide was crystallised from alcohol (95%) and obtained in fine prismatic needles, m. p. 181-82° (uncorrected) (Fig. 1). This was dissolved in calculated amount of 2*N*-caustic soda solution, cooled and slowly treated with freshly prepared silver nitrate solution. The silver salt at once precipitated out, was filtered, washed with water to make it free from silver ion and then with absolute alcohol and dried in *vacuo* in the dark. It gradually acquired a tint on exposure to light

The silver salt was then suspended in dry benzene and refluxed with ethyl iodide (1.25 mole) for 1 hour. Silver iodide was found to separate out. The reaction mixture was filtered, and the filtrate was evaporated under diminished pressure to remove most of the benzene when crystals began to separate. On cooling, crystals were collected and dried over a blotting paper, and recrystallised from dilute alcohol (1:1) in fine elongated rectangular rods (Fig. 2). It melted at 183° (uncorrected).

The filter from the above reaction mixture was extracted with alcohol (95%) by refluxing. The alcoholic solution was filtered and concentrated on a boiling water-bath. Crystals separated out. These were collected and recrystallised from dilute alcohol (1:1) in hexagons, m. p. 189° (uncorrected) (Fig. 3). An analysis of both types of crystals for nitrogen and sulphur gave the following results.

[Found (rectangular rods, m. p. 183°): N, 9.53; S, 10.45. (hexagons, m. p. 189°): N, 9.49; S, 10.41. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.2; S, 10.52 per cent).

The yield-ratio of 'Rods' variety to "Hexagons" was about 20 : 50.

General Properties.—Both forms are insoluble in water, readily dissolve in alkali and are precipitated on acidification. They are partly soluble in acids but neither the soluble portions nor the insoluble parts give diazo reaction. Both respond to secondary amine test. A mixture of the two in equal proportion melts indifferently at 165°.

They were then subjected to acid-hydrolysis. For this 0.5 g. of each form was refluxed with 20 c.c. of 10% hydrochloric acid for 5 hours. The container was cooled when a white crystalline substance separated out. This was identified as benzoic acid. The filtrate was neutralised with sodium carbonate when another white substance was precipitated. This was collected and crystallised from boiling water (charcoal). The crop isolated from "Rectangular rods" separated in rhombic plates, m. p. 135° (Fig. 4) and the one obtained from "Hexagons" was leaf-like in structure, melting at 137° (Fig. 5). A mixture of the two in equal proportion melted at 111-14°.

An analysis of both types of these crystals for nitrogen again gave the following results :—

[Found (Rhombic plates, m. p. 135°): N, 13.98. (Leaf-like crystals, m. p. 137°), N, 14.09. $C_8H_8NH.C_6H_4SO_2NH_2$ requires N, 14.0 per cent].

Both are partly soluble in water, readily dissolve in alkali, and partly soluble in dilute acid. The acid solution, however, gave no diazo reaction. In consulting the literature it was noticed that N¹-ethylsulphanilamide is of prismatic needles and melts at 106-107° (Mangini, *Chem. Abs.*, 1943, 37, 98). One N⁴-ethylsulphanilamide has been isolated by us by reacting silver salt of sulphanilamide with ethyl iodide (described in another paper), and found to melt at 135° without sintering when admixed with the rhombic plates as previously isolated by hydrolysis of the rectangular rods variety of ethyl sulphanilylbenzamide.

Reaction with Methyl Iodide.—Similarly silver salt of sulphanilylbenzamide was reacted with methyl iodide in benzene suspension as in the previous case. The benzene filtrate afforded a small quantity of a crystal, m. p. 155°, whereas the filter on extraction with alcohol (95%) gave a good yield of another product crystallising from dilute alcohol (1 : 1) in fine needles, m. p. 142°.

They on analysis gave nitrogen, 9.81 and 9.74% respectively. Methyl derivative of sulphanilylbenzamide ($C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S$) requires N, 9.65 %.

Neither is soluble in acids but each readily dissolves in alkali. On hydrolysing the crop, m. p. 142°, by dilute hydrochloric acid as usual, benzoic acid separated out on cooling. The hydrolysed solution on neutralisation with

sodium carbonate afforded N⁺-methylsulphanilamide. This crystallised from dilute alcohol in rectangular plates, melting at 210-11° (uncorrected). To ascertain its constitution silver salt of sulphanilamide was refluxed with methyl iodide in benzene suspension for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was filtered and the benzene solution was allowed to cool. Crystals separating were collected and recrystallised from dilute alcohol. It melted at 210-11° without depressing when mixed with equal part of the above N⁺-methylsulphanilamide, the corresponding N⁺-methylsulphanilamide melting at 111-12° (*cf. Mangini, loc. cit.*).

It may be noticed that when the silver salts of the N⁺-benzoylsulphanilamide (sulphanilylbenzamide) are reacted with an alkyl iodide, the N⁺-hydrogen atom is always being substituted by the alkyl radical. The alkylated compounds obtained are soluble in alkali and form silver salts, but the latter, no more react with ethyl iodide and may be recovered practically unchanged from the reaction mixture. Similarly N⁺-acetyl-N⁺-benzoylsulphanilamide is soluble in alkali, forms silver salt but cannot be further alkylated.

Fig. 1
Sulphanilylbenzamide ($\times 80$)

Fig. 2
N'-Ethyl sulphanilylbenzamide ($\times 80$)

Fig. 3.
N'-Ethyl sulphanilyl-
benzamide ($\times 225$)

Fig. 4.
N'-Ethyl sulphanilamide
($\times 225$)

Fig. 5.
N'-Ethyl sulphanilamide
($\times 100$)

